

EFFECT OF SHARAPUNKHA KSHAR PRATISARAN ON GARBHASHAY GRIVAGAT VRANA (CERVICAL EROSION)

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ABSTRACT

This clinical study evaluated the effect of *Sharapunkha Kshar Pratisaran* in the management of *Garbhashay Grivagat Vrana* (Cervical Ectopy), a prevalent gynecological condition characterized by the replacement of squamous epithelium with columnar epithelium on the cervix. Symptoms such as vaginal discharge, pruritus vulvae, and backache cause significant discomfort. A single-arm clinical intervention was conducted on 20 women aged 18-49 years, presenting with classical symptoms. *Sharapunkha Kshar* was applied locally once daily for 7 days. Efficacy was assessed using subjective (itching, backache) and objective (discharge, site, size, appearance of ectopy) parameters on baseline, day 3, and day 7. Statistical analysis (Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test) showed significant improvement across all parameters ($p < 0.0001$). Average symptomatic relief was 72.24%, with 40% cured ($\geq 75\%$ relief) and 60% markedly improved ($50 < 75\%$ relief). The therapy was safe and well tolerated. Results suggest *Sharapunkha*

Kshar Pratisaran is effective due to its *vrana shodhan*, *ropan*, anti-inflammatory, and astringent properties. Larger controlled studies are recommended.

KEYWORDS: Cervical erosion, Garbhashay Grivagat Vrana, Kshar Pratisaran, Karnini Yonivyapad, ulcer healing, vaginal discharge, Sharapunkha.

INTRODUCTION

Women's reproductive health is often neglected due to sociocultural priorities. Cervical ectopy (*Garbhashay Grivagat Vrana*), though not life-threatening, causes morbidity through abnormal discharge, itching, and backache. Modern treatments like cauterization and laser vaporization have disadvantages, whereas Ayurveda offers safe alternatives. This study evaluates the role of *Sharapunkha Kshar Pratisaran* in symptom relief and tissue healing in cervical ectopy.

Objective: To evaluate the effect of *Sharapunkha Kshar Pratisaran* in managing *Garbhashay Grivagat Vrana* over 7 days.

Methods

Study Design: Single-arm clinical interventional study

Setting: SMBT Ayurveda College & Hospital, Nandi Hill, Dhamangaon, Maharashtra

Duration: Sept 2024 – Jan 2025

Sample: 20 married women, aged 18–49 years, symptomatic with cervical ectopy

Inclusion Criteria: Married, symptomatic (discharge, pruritus, backache), controlled diabetes.

Exclusion Criteria: Pregnant, postpartum, unmarried, malignancy, irregular follow-up.

Intervention

- Drug: *Sharapunkha Kshar* (prepared classically)
- Route: Local cervical application (*Pratisaran*) with cotton swab
- Frequency: Once daily × 7 days post-menstruation
- Dose: Sufficient to cover ectopic area, followed by washing

Assessment Parameters

- *Subjective:* Pruritus vulvae, backache (VAS)
- *Objective:* Discharge (appearance & quantity), ectopy site, appearance, size

Sr. no	Parameter	Scale / Grade description
1.	Pruritus Vulvae	0 = Absent; 1 = Occasional; 2 = Daily; 3 = Intolerable
2.	Backache (VAS)	0 = None; 1 = Mild (1–3); 2 = Mod. (4–7); 3 = Severe (8–10)
3.	Discharge Appearance	0 = Clear; 1 = Flecks of pus; 2 = <50% mucopurulent; 3 = >50% white or yellow purulent pus
4.	Discharge Quantity	0 = None; 1 = Moistening; 2 = Staining underwear; 3 = Pads required

5.	Ectopy Site	0 = None; 1–4 = Quadrants of cervix affected
6.	Appearance	0 = Normal; 1 = Pink to Red; 2 = Red; 3 = Red- velvety; 4 =red velvety with Nabothian cysts
7.	Size	0 = 0–25%; 1 = 26–50%; 2 = 51–75%; 3 = 76– 100%

Statistical Analysis: Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test for pre- and post-treatment.

Procedure

Purva Karma: Preparation of *Triphala Kwath* for vaginal douching. Instruments sterilized. Vaginal passage washed with ~2L lukewarm decoction via enema pot.

Pradhana Karma: After drying, cotton swab dipped in *Sharapunkha Kshar* applied to cervix for 1 minute, followed by *Yoni Prakshalan* with *Nimbu Swarasa*. Sim's speculum/AV retractor used for visualization.

RESULTS

Significant improvement noted in subjective and objective criteria ($p < 0.05$).

Symptoms	BT	AT	Relieved	% Relief
Pruritus vulvae	37	8	29	78.38
Backache	30	8	22	73.33
Vaginal discharge appearance	39	12	27	69.23
Vaginal discharge quantity	39	12	27	69.23
Site of ectopy	57	16	41	71.93
Appearance of ectopy	39	11	28	71.79
Size of ectopy	280	79	201	71.79
	Average % Relief	72.24		

Average symptomatic relief: **72.24%** 40% cured, 60% markedly improved.

Improvement	No. of Patients	%
Unchanged	0	0%
Mild	0	0%
Marked	12	60%
Cured	8	40%
Total	20	100%

Vyadhi Samprapti (Pathogenesis)

- *Tridoshaja Ahara–Vihara* → mainly *Kapha–Pitta* vitiation
- *Agnimandya* → *Rasavaha Strotas Dushti*
- Involvement of *Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa*
- *Dosha–Dushya Samurchana* at *Garbhashay Griva* → *Khavaigunya* → *Garbhashay Grivagat Vrana*

Mode of Action**Pharmacological properties of Sharapunkha Kshar**

Sr. No.	Properties	Action	Effect
1	Tikta, Kashaya rasa, Ruksha, Ushna	Kaphapitta Shamak	Reduces discharge & <i>kleda</i>
2	Tikta rasa, Laghu, Ushna	Agnidipana, Strotoshodhan, <i>Dushtamansahar</i>	Removes columnar epithelium, promotes squamous re-epithelialization
3	Kashaya rasa, Laghu	Vranaropan	Accelerates healing
4	Tikta rasa	Kapha–Pitta Shaman	Reduces <i>Yonikandu</i>
5	Ushna virya	Kapha–Vata Shamak	Reduces pain & inflammation

Mode of Action of Kshar

Sharapunkha kshar	Tikshna, ushna, laghu, chedan, shodhan, lekhanaya karama	Destruct the coloumnar epithelium
Roopan, shoshan, sankochan	Re-epithelization of squamous epithelium in place of columnar epithelium	
Tikshna, krimihar, vishhara	Minimize entry or development of any infection	
Stambhana, shoshana	Decreases the amount of vaginal discharge	

- *Tikshna, Ushna, Laghu, Chedan, Shodhan, Lekhaniya* → destruction of columnar epithelium
- *Roopan, Shoshan, Sankochan* → re-epithelialization of squamous cells
- *Krimighna, Vishaghna* → prevents infection
- *Stambhana, Shoshana* → reduces discharge

DISCUSSION

This study demonstrated significant relief in symptoms and lesion healing within 7 days of *Sharapunkha Kshar Pratisaran*. Findings align with earlier reports on *Kshar* and herbal *Yoniprakashalana*. Mechanism is multifactorial: debridement, cleansing (*Vranashodhan*), tissue repair, and prevention of infection. Minimal side effects noted.

Limitations: small sample, no control group. Larger trials required.

CONCLUSION

Sharapunkha Kshar Pratisaran is effective, safe, and well-tolerated in managing *Garbhashay Grivagat Vrana*. It provides rapid relief with an average improvement of 72%. It offers a promising non-invasive alternative to cauterization with minimal recurrence.

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